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Developing Solutions for Underwater Radiated Noise

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Report on Particle Motion and Acoustic Pressure measurements in the AquaVib

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Executive Summary

The development and testing of new methodologies to establish dose-response relationships for physiological, pathological and behavioural responses quantification of marine invertebrates to controlled exposure to URN, where both the acoustic pressure (AP), and the particle motion (PM) components are evaluated separately (SATURN Task 3.1), is one of the approaches proposed to cover Objective 2 of SATURN project: to be able to advance our knowledge on the acute and cumulative effects of underwater noise on aquatic species.

SATURN subtask 3.1.1. addresses the development of new technologies to estimate the comparative effects of these two sound components of URN signals' features from ships and boats developed in the SATURN subtask 2.1.2.

The *AquaVib* system, developed by the LAB-UPC research group, permits controlled exposure of invertebrate species at any of their mature stages to URN signals, where both sound components can be separately and quantitatively assessed.

Introduction

The Acoustic Pressure (AP) component of a sound wave is currently the only parameter used to investigate the possible effects of sound cues on aquatic life. However, recent literature revealed invertebrate species to be especially sensitive to the particle motion (PM) component, particularly below 1kHz (Popper & Hawkins, 2018).

Due to the high complexity of field-based studies, the UPC research group has developed, advised by SATURN partner TNO, a laboratory setup named *AquaVib* (SATURN Subtask 3.1.1), which allows for controlled exposures of marine invertebrates to artificially synthesized ship sound signals (SATURN Subtask 2.1.2). This is based on the *Larvaebrator* setup, designed and built by TNO (Bolle, et al., 2012).

As previously reported (Martin & Rogers, 2008; Schulz-Mirbach, et al., 2020), the control of the relative phase between a pair of 1 kN-electrodynamical (ED) shakers allow for generating either an acoustic-pressure- or a particle-motion-dominated exposure sound field within a water-filled rigid vessel that is closed at both ends by the pair of ED shakers. More precisely, within the AquaVib chambers, both far-field, i.e. the potential and the kinetic energies carried by the sound wave are in the same order of magnitude, and near-field patterns, i.e. the kinetic energy being significantly larger than the potential energy, can be simulated.

In parallel, the AquaVib permits tracking of the metabolic rate and behavioural reactions of the exposed animals in real time thanks to an embedded respirometry system and a see-through acoustic chamber.

The present document provides a detailed characterization of the AquaVib system, preceded by a description of the intended setup based on the current state-of-the-art, and the main aspects covered during the design and building processes to fulfil the SATURN Subtask 3.1.1. main goal described in the Description of Action of the SATURN project.

1. Technical specifications of the desired laboratory setup

1.1. Review of literature: Reference systems

The design and the underlying concept of the AquaVib are based on previously reported systems (Martin & Rogers, 2008; Halvorsen, et al., 2011; Bolle, et al., 2012; Halvorsen, et al., 2012; Schulz-Mirbach, et al., 2020), whose main goal was to reliably separate the energy contribution of the two sound field components: Particle Motion (PM), and Acoustic Pressure (AP).

1.1.1. High Intensity Controlled Impedance – Fluid filled wave Tube

The *High Intensity Controlled Impedance – Fluid filled wave Tube* (HICI-FT) (Halvorsen, et al., 2011; Halvorsen, et al., 2012), and the Larvaebrator (Bolle, et al., 2012), were used as the two main reference systems for the design of the AquaVib.

Designed and constructed by the same research group in charge of the *Fishabrator* system (Martin & Rogers, 2008), the HICI-FT “enabled replication of aquatic far-field, plane-wave acoustic conditions in the laboratory” (Halvorsen, et al., 2011). It consisted of a pair of 670 N ED shakers (Vibration Test Systems, VG-150 Vibration Generator, Model VTS 150), that capped a 38.1 mm-thick stainless steel cylinder of 22-litre volume. It was also equipped with a calibrated hydrophone (Model 8103, Brüel & Kjær, Denmark), and an encapsulated accelerometer (MISTRAS, Vibra-Metrics Model 9002) [see Halvorsen et al. (2011), Appendix G for more details].

Figure 1 - The HICI-FT in the horizontal and vertical positions. A) The HICI-FT in the vertical position for loading fish into the acrylic chamber. The top shaker is detached from the tube and is surrounded by grey PVC to protect it from the water in the acrylic chamber. B) During treatments the HICI-FT is in the horizontal position.. The red structure is the supporting frame, the white PVC pipes drain the water, and the grey hoses are part of the shaker cooling system. [From Halvorsen (2012)]

The *HICI-FT* was used to simulate the far-field sound propagation of real high-intensity pile driving sounds (up to 215 dB SPL_{peak} re 1 μPa^2), in a parametrically controlled setup, to quantify the effects on fish physiology. By controlling the relative phase between the driving shakers, the researchers created either a pressure- (0 degrees) or velocity-dominated (180 degrees) field within the water column enclosed inside the stainless steel tube for the sound exposure of the animals (Halvorsen, et al., 2011).

1.1.2. The larvaebibrator

As stated by its authors (Bolle, et al., 2012): “The general ‘larvaebibrator’ design concept consists of an LFPX-4 projector [...] on which a rigged-walled (28 mm thick) cylindrical chamber (110 mm diameter, 160 mm high) is placed [...]. The chamber is filled with seawater and the larvae. The piston of the projector is also the bottom of the chamber and can directly excite the water with a given signal.

Depending on the required boundary conditions, i.e. constant pressure or constant velocity, the top cover [...] of the chamber can be closed (pressure excitation) or released (velocity excitation). The sound pressure in the chamber is measured by four pressure transducers, mounted flush in the wall of the chamber. The sound particle velocity is measured by a waterproof accelerometer, mounted on the piston of the projector”.

Figure 2 - Laboratory setup Larvaebibrator (Bolle, et al., 2011)

In addition to these systems, the *Plexiglas® standing wave tube-like setup* system (Schulz-Mirbach, et al., 2020), inspired the UPC research group to use a transparent acoustic chamber to perform behavioural studies while the animals are exposed to a controlled sound field.

1.2. Terms and definitions

The metrics used in this report follow the terminology described in ISO 18405:2017 (ISO, 2017).

SPL (re. 1 μPa^2) and SVL (re. 1 nm/s) stand for the time-average mean-square sound pressure and sound particle velocity levels respectively.

To get an estimate of the particle velocity employing acceleration sensors, the following rationale is applied:

$$L_u = L_a - 20\log(2\pi f) + 60 \text{ dB} \quad (1)$$

where

L_u , previously referenced as SVL, is the time-averaged mean-square sound particle velocity level (re 1 nm/s),

L_a is the time-averaged mean-square sound particle acceleration level (re 1 $\mu\text{m/s}^2$),

f is the frequency expressed in Hz,

and the addition of 60 dB corresponds to the unit conversion between L_u and L_a .

The total energy carried by a sound wave is made up of the sum of its potential energy (E_{pot}), and its kinetic energy (E_{kin}), which are directly related to the compression and rarefaction of the medium (pressure waves), and the motion of the particles that constitute the propagation medium, respectively. Thus, sound pressure p , and sound particle velocity u can be expressed in terms of E_{pot} and E_{kin} as:

$$E_{pot} = \overline{p^2}/(2\rho c^2) \quad (2)$$

$$E_{kin} = \overline{\rho u^2}/2 \quad (3)$$

where ρ ($\sim 1.03 \text{ g/cm}^3$) and c ($\sim 1500 \text{ m/s}$) are the density of and sound propagation velocity in seawater respectively.

By expressing (2) and (3) in dB levels (re 1 $\mu\text{Pa}^2\text{m}^2/\text{s}$):

$$L_{E_{pot}} = 10\log(\overline{p^2}/2\rho c^2 E_0) = 10\log(\overline{p^2}/p_0^2) + 10\log(p_0^2/2\rho c^2 E_0) = L_p + 10\log(p_0^2/2\rho c^2 E_0) \text{ dB} \quad (4)$$

$$L_{E_{kin}} = 10\log(\overline{\rho u^2}/2 E_0) = 10\log(\overline{u^2}/u_0^2) + 10\log(\rho u_0^2/2 E_0) = L_u + 10\log(\rho u_0^2/2 E_0) \text{ dB} \quad (5)$$

where L_p and L_u correspond to the aforementioned SPL and SVL metrics respectively. The energy ratio can be expressed as:

$$L_{E_{pot}} - L_{E_{kin}} = L_p - L_u - 10\log((\rho c)^2 u_0^2/p_0^2) = L_p - L_u - 64 \text{ dB} \quad (6)$$

In free-field conditions, i.e. far from the source and any acoustic boundary, the radiated sound pressure coming from an acoustic point source¹ is inversely proportional to the distance from the source, and thus the energy components of the sound field, i.e. E_{pot} and E_{kin} , are considered to be equal. Therefore, from (6) it can be derived that under acoustic free-field conditions:

$$L_p - L_u = 10\log((\rho c)^2 u_0^2/p_0^2) \text{ dB} \approx 64 \text{ dB} \quad (7)$$

¹ A point source (monopole) is a hypothetical acoustic source that radiates homnidirectionally. This approximation is valid when the source is much smaller than the largests wavelength emitted (Nedelec, et al., 2021)

In contrast, when the aforementioned conditions are not held (e.g. at the source near-field, in shallow waters, close to acoustic boundaries), the particle velocity component of the sound field carries most of the energy ($E_{kin} > E_{pot}$) (Popper & Hawkins, 2018), and thus the approximation defined in equation (7) is no longer valid.

1.3. Target system performance and required features

Initially, it was planned to build three units of the *Larvaebrator* to accomplish Task 3.1. However, due to technical constraints derived from its design (e.g. small volume of its acoustic chamber, the LFPX-4 acoustic projector not being available in the market anymore, etc.), the UPC proposed, following the concept for PM-AP decoupling presented by other authors (Martin & Rogers, 2008; Halvorsen, et al., 2012; Schulz-Mirbach, et al., 2020), to design and build a larger system that could provide broader applicability, i.e. larger volume to work with larger animals, interchangeable acoustic chambers, respirometry module, behavioural studies, etc.

To fulfil the main goal of Task 3.1, AquaVib's main requirements were to accurately reproduce low-frequency URN broadband signals, (i.e. below 500 Hz where most of the ships URN energy is concentrated), at representative levels and in such a way that the sound energy components could be controlled, i.e. both potential and kinetic energies, whilst also enabling the animals' respiration rate and behaviour to be tracked during exposure.

The main considerations during the design stage and the adopted solutions are as follows:

1.3.1. Handling of animals

Animals are maintained in filtered natural seawater at 18-22°C, salinity 35 g/l, and natural oxygen pressure, in the LAB maintenance tank system before, during, and after the exposure. This closed system of recirculating natural seawater consists of two mechanically filtered fibreglass-reinforced plastic tanks of 2000 L capacity, that are connected. This includes a physicochemical self-filtration system with activated carbon and sand, driven by two circulation pumps (see Figure 21 in section A.2. Outdoor facilities). The AquaVib is connected to it, so the same water conditions are maintained during the acclimatization and exposure periods.

Thus, the whole setup design makes it possible to prevent animals from being harmed.

1.3.2. Sound field

COMPARATIVE EFFECT OF THE ACOUSTIC ENERGIES

The AquaVib is equipped with a pair of 1 kN ED shakers, each of which has an IEPE accelerometer attached to its plate. The control over the relative phase between the pair of shakers in two different configuration modes, i.e. AP and PM configuration, permits control of the energy contribution of each of the two sound field components, i.e. E_{pot} and E_{kin} .

HIGH-LEVEL SOUND FIELDS PRODUCTION

A container ship can reach up to 188 dB, re 1 μ Pa@1 m (McKenna, et al., 2012). In general, most ships' sound energy is concentrated below 1 kHz, among which the lower frequency components (< 200 Hz) can normally propagate furthest (e.g. > 110 dB re 1 μ Pa@10-20 km from the source) (Jones, 2021).

As described by Bolle et al. (2012) by simple formulation, the needed force to generate a peak pressure level of 210 dB re 1 μ Pa driven by a 160 mm-diameter rigid piston would be 643 N.

The pair of 1 kN ED shakers mounted in the AquaVib are driven by each 108 mm-diameter rigid piston. Therefore, the theoretical maximum peak pressure level they can reach is 220 dB re 1 μ Pa with no payload.

SYSTEM'S RESPONSE CORRECTION

Shakers are widely used in industry to evaluate the response to vibrations of a vast range of goods: from microchips to whole aircraft. However, they are not built specifically to provide a uniform-spectrum response, unlike professional audio transducers. Therefore, the use of these devices for sound reproduction compelled us to apply an equalization routine over the input signal to compensate for the whole playback system response.

The AquaVib system counts with a dedicated module to perform the correction of the input signal to compensate for the setup Frequency Response Function (FRF), i.e. shakers' FRF curves, support-structure- and ground-borne vibrations, shakers relative phase, mass payload, etc.

DECOUPLING OF THE WATER COLUMN FROM THE OUTER

A highly-dense rigid-wall container and proper isolation of the support structure to vibrations are essential to mitigate unwanted colouration of the sound field presented within the water column (Bolle, et al., 2011; Halvorsen, et al., 2011) (e.g. fluid-shell coupling effects (Fuller & Fahy, 1982), ground- and structural-borne vibrations). As stated by Schulz-Mirbach et al. (2020), a stainless steel tube of at least 10 mm thick would be needed for our frequencies of interest.

The current AquaVib has been prepared with three different tubes: two of 30 mm-thick carbon steel walls S355J2H (7.7-8.03 g/cm³), and the third one of 9 mm-thick borosilicate glass (2.7 g/cm³), which is more than twice as dense as methyl methacrylate, i.e. Plexyglass[®]. 1.18 g/cm³. Despite the borosilicate glass cylinder does not perfectly fulfil the requirements described in the preceding paragraph, satisfactory system performance is achieved in terms of spectral response, as demonstrated below in section 3, while allowing visual inspection of the enclosed water volume.

Furthermore, the whole system is supported by a rigid structure made of 5 mm-thick square bars of structural steel. In turn, it was screwed into a 20 cm-thick concrete platform at the outdoor facilities of the LAB.

WAVE PROPAGATION

To allow for an estimate of the comparative effects of both acoustic components, i.e. AP and PM, no wave propagation can be present in the water container. As stated by Bolle et al. (2011), the largest dimension of the water container is restricted to one-sixth of the smallest wavelength of interest.

The largest dimension of the three acoustic chambers that the AquaVib has available is 500 mm for the large steel tube, and 250 mm for both the small steel tube and the transparent borosilicate tube. Thus, in water (~1500 ms⁻¹ sound speed), the theoretical upper-frequency limits are 500 Hz and 1 kHz respectively.

1.3.3. Behavioural and physiological assessment

Physiological assessment is achieved by an accurate estimation of the animals' metabolic rate, which is linked to the amount of oxygen depletion in the water volume. Its correct estimate tightly depends upon a fine control of (i) water temperature, (ii) dissolved oxygen, and (iii) water flow rate in the confined water column.

From the review of the literature (Bolduc, et al., 2002; Watson, et al., 2014; Rodgers, et al., 2016; Morozov, et al., 2019; Ruiz-Ruiz, et al., 2019; Wale, et al., 2019; Aimon, et al., 2021), and research on the built-in systems available in the market, the FireSting®-O2 Optical Oxygen Meter (PyroScience GmbH, Germany), was found to be the most suitable for this application.

To get reliable reads from the device, the manufacturer highlighted that: (i) the water temperature must not drift further than ± 0.5 °C, (ii) the water flow through the temperature-oxygen cell could not exceed 500 ml/min during the whole experiment, and (iii) the tubing used to drive the water sample through the respirometry cell has to ensure low oxygen permeability.

To accomplish these requirements, an auxiliary water circuit was built to connect a UPC-owned water cooling-filtering system with the AquaVib. Besides, a low-power inline water pump (Syncra NANO, SICCE S.r.l., Italy) and PTFE-FEP 4.0x6.0 mm tubing (Bohlender GmbH, Germany) were used to ensure a correct water flow rate with a low oxygen permeability. The continuous monitoring and automated control of both the dissolved oxygen content and the temperature of the water, prevent any possible animal damage caused by an excessive drift of the initial ambient conditions.

Aside, the use of a digital camera inserted into the acoustic chamber was first considered to monitor possible animal reactions. However, it was dismissed due to the technical constraints it implied to get quality images for behavioural assessment during the exposure (e.g. the need for a light source, the insertion and location of the camera, the maximum viewing angle, etc.). As an alternative, the use of a transparent-borosilicate cylinder was preferred for its simplicity, which provides a clear vision of the enclosed water column for behavioural assessment.

1.3.4. System handling

Comfortable and safe handling of the system was carefully considered in the design, for both animals' and technicians' safety.

Due to the size and weight of the components and the materials used to build the AquaVib system, the support structure was designed to assist the operator/s in the system handling. See section 2.2.4 for more details on the structure design/construction.

1.3.5. Economics

The main economic challenge in the design was to get a pair of ED shakers that fitted within the assigned budget for Task 3.1.1. The offers received from the most renowned providers of vibration testing equipment (e.g. IMV Corporation, Sentek, B&K) were over 20 k€ per unit.

A simpler pair of 1 kN ED shakers, plus the adaption of an audio professional amplifier for this purpose, was found to be the best alternative to fit into the assigned budget, keeping a safety margin to cope with unexpected events during the building and fine-tuning processes.

2. System description

2.1. Preliminary tests

Courtesy of the SATURN partner TNO, the UPC research group got the opportunity to first study the relation between the two sound field components, i.e. AP and PM, on the *Larvaebrator* system (Solé, et al., 2022).

The *Larvaebrator* acoustic chamber – with its embedded sensors –, was later included in a setup to perform two preliminary tests sessions with a professional vibration test system kindly provided by Mr Xavier Corbella from Álava Ingenieros, Grupo Álava (Spain). It included: (i) a 600 N ED shaker (M60, IMV Corporation, Japan), (ii) an amplification system (MA1-CE, IMV Corporation, Japan), and (iii) a control module (Spider 81, Crystal Instruments, USA).

The following aspects were investigated during these two sessions:

- The use of an ED shaker to adequately produce both high-intensity pressure and velocity fields within the water column.
- Familiarization with, and understanding of the correct setup and manipulation of ED shakers, and their main physical and electrical constraints (e.g. displacement, velocity and acceleration limits as a function of frequency; current and voltage modes).
- Identify the main factors involved in the setup (e.g. shaker-to-water column coupling interface, support structure, sensors location), to correctly interpret the relation between the output exerted force, and both measured sound pressure and particle acceleration.
- Frequency Response Function (FRF) of ED shakers, and their capability to feasibly reproduce a broadband signal (e.g. ship noise).
- Sound Pressure Level (SPL) measured in the water column as a function of the exerted force-acceleration generated by the shaker at different frequencies, and different acceleration rates.
- Effect of an air gap on top of the acoustic chamber concerning the “water-filled” configuration, measured at different frequencies and different accelerations.
- Use of an audio amplifier as an alternative to power ED shakers.
- The need for a 2-channels active control module, to automatically adjust the response of the shakers².

To this purpose, the acoustic chamber of the *Larvaebrator* was firmly mounted on top of a hand-made support structure (Figure 3), where some additional weight was added to minimize both the ground-borne and structural vibrations to the water column.

See Bolle et al. (2011) for more details on the *Larvaebrator* and its mounted sensors

² The use of stand-alone active control systems is common practice in vibration testing industry (e.g. the aforementioned Spider 81 from Crystal Instruments). They actively correct ED shakers response drifts during vibration tests, to be kept within the pre-set amplitude and frequency parameters.

Figure 3 - Set-up during the two preliminary tests sessions. The control module lies on top of the amplification module. The Larvaibrator acoustic chamber was screwed onto a 5 mm structural steel plate. The ED shaker was located beneath it, right on top of the concrete foundation.

The coupling between the ED shaker and the water column enclosed in the *Larvaibrator* chamber was done through a 5 mm-metal piston, as shown in Figure 4.

Close care was put to ensure that the piston tightly matched the EPDM membrane that supported the water from the bottom of the cylinder.

The transfer function of the piston was evaluated using a second accelerometer (as shown in the aforementioned figure) and could be verified to have a flat spectral response below 1 kHz.

Figure 4 - ED shaker and the metal piston to couple the generated vibrations to the enclosed water column at the Larvaebrator acoustic chamber. The top accelerometer was employed at the beginning of the first session to evaluate the piston's transfer function. The bottom accelerometer was used during the two sessions to track the acceleration curve output by the ED shaker.

In most of the tests an acceleration ramp-up (0.1 g to 16 g), centred at different pure tones (100 Hz, 200 Hz, 400 Hz, 600 Hz and 800 Hz) was employed as the input signal. These ramp-ups were continuously actively controlled by the aforementioned module *Spyder 81*.

For simplicity, no quantitative results from these two sessions are reported here, however a number of important qualitative conclusions were drawn based on expert opinion (Xavier Corbella, *pers comm*), and the observed performance of the setup during the two test sessions. These conclusions, which helped to inform subsequent stages of project planning, are summarised below:

- The transfer function of ED shakers resembles a mass-spring system.
- A broadly ~6 dB linear increment in SPL was observed by doubling the acceleration for every frequency band.
- The SPL obtained at different acceleration ranges is dependent upon the input frequency.
- A significant reduction in SPL was confirmed when a few centimetres of air gap was left at the top of the acoustic chamber.
- A properly built support structure is crucial: (i) to eliminate unwanted resonances of the “shaker-cylinder-water column” mass volume, and to mitigate (ii) the transmission losses from the water

column to its surrounding and (iii) any significant colouration of the generated sound field spectrum derived from present air- or structural-borne background vibrations.

- Due to the large energy output needed from the ED shakers to produce a high-intensity exposure (in power and time) within the water column, they need to be properly scaled so that they are always below their maximum performance curve in displacement, velocity and acceleration, to avoid system overstress.

Figure 5 - 100% Sine Performance chart of the GW-V55/DSA5-1K system, from Data Physics Corporation. Courtesy of ARIES Ingeniería y sistemas, S.A.

- Close care has to be taken to get a proper piston-membrane coupling. Otherwise, the transmission of the vibrations from the shaker to the water column is very poor.
- The maximum load mass, i.e. max. shaker suspension static payload support, of ED shakers within our range of interest, is around 10-12 kg.
- A dedicated system to control in real time the response of the system is of significant help. Nonetheless, given the offers received, the high price of these systems was also remarkable (from 10k€ on for a single channel one).
- ED shakers are suited for high-intensity broadband signal playback (<2 kHz). Figure 6 shows a comparison between a field-recorded ship sound (bottom) and the pre-filtered played-back one (top) for visual inspection. A more detailed evaluation of this aspect is provided below in this text (see section 3.3).

Figure 6 - Visual comparison of a field recording of ship noise (bottom), and the pre-filtered shaker played back one (top).

This phase of the design process was important in revealing a number of uncertainties that the UPC research group would need to take into account in order to ensure that the system performance would enable the project goals to be attained.

2.2. AquaVib – Laboratory experimental set-up

As stated in the introductory section, one of the main project's goals stated in Task 3.1 is to quantify the impact of URN on aquatic invertebrates by employing new techniques that allow for an evaluation of the effects of particle motion (PM) and acoustic pressure (AP) onto the health status (physiological, pathological, ultrastructural) and behaviour of the exposed animals.

As such, the researcher team at the UPC have equipped the AquaVib system with a series of functionalities to allow for a simultaneous evaluation of the aforementioned variables in a controlled environment.

Figure 7 - General view of the AquaVib system. The large 500 mm-long steel tube is mounted.

The AquaVib system consists of a pair of 1 kN ED shakers, that enclose at both ends a rigid-walled water-filled acoustic chamber, where the input energy that the animals are exposed to can be configured and controlled so that they receive a significantly higher dose of kinetic energy (particle motion, PM) compared to potential energy (acoustic pressure, AP), and vice versa. Furthermore, by incorporating a respiration module and a transparent acoustic chamber, the AquaVib is also equipped to concomitantly evaluate possible correlations with changes in animals' health and behaviour when exposed.

For simplicity in the description of the entire setup the follows, individual components have been grouped under four separate headings.

2.2.1. Exposure module

A pair of 1 kN ED shakers (JZK-100, Sinocera Piezotronics Inc., China) are used as acoustic projectors to generate a realistic broadband sound field that is representative of the energy input from URN that the animals would be exposed to in the wild. By controlling the relative phase in two different modes, i.e. Acoustic Pressure (AP) configuration at 0°, vs. Particle Motion (PM) configuration at 180°, either kinetic energy- or potential energy-dominated sound field can be created within the water volume, whilst maintaining the energy distribution of the target sound cue (further details are presented below in section 3).

The shakers are powered through a 2-channel audio amplifier of up to 2 kW per channel (ICE-4000, AudioLab, UK).

The experimental set-up is equipped with three different acoustic chambers that can be easily interchanged depending on test-specific requirements (e.g. behaviour studies, large animals, larger frequency range): (i) a large 30 mm-thick carbon steel acoustic chamber (7.7-8.03 g/cm³) of 500 mm length (L) x 238.5 mm internal diameter (ID); (ii) a small 30 mm-thick carbon steel acoustic chamber of 250 mm L x 150 mm ID; and (iii) 9 mm-thick borosilicate glass acoustic chamber (2.7 g/cm³) of 250 mm L x 152 mm ID.

The test configuration and the playback of the desired signals, plus some of the main functionalities of the *AquaVib* system are configured and controlled through a dedicated graphical user interface (GUI) programmed in the Python language (Python Software Foundation, USA). This is accessible to the users through a 10" touchscreen (AIO-CM4-101, Chipsee, China), with an embedded Raspberry Pi CM4 module (Raspberry Pi Foundation, UK).

Figure 8 - Screenshot of the AquaVib GUI main page.

2.2.2. Acquisition module

Sound pressure is acquired by a pair of flush-mounted hydrophones (BII-7114, Benthowave Instrument Inc., Canada) of -201 dB re. 1V/ 1 μ P. These are located 5 cm from the right end, and in the longitudinal centre of the acoustic chamber respectively³.

The particle velocity is acquired by a pair of IEPE accelerometers (805-0050, TE Connectivity Ltd., USA) of 100 mV/g, respectively placed at the rear face of both shakers' moving heads. These are controlled by a CCLD signal conditioner (Type 1704-A-001, Brüel & Kjær Sound & Vibration Measurement A/S · DK-2850 Nærum · Denmark).

The analogue signals acquired by the pair of hydrophones and the pair of accelerometers are digitalized by a USB-1608G DAQ (Measurement Computing Corporation, USA).

Both dissolved oxygen and water temperature are autonomously measured by the FireSting[®]-O₂ Optical Oxygen Meter (PyroScience GmbH, Deutschland), where both the TOFTC2 (sample's dissolved oxygen and temperature) and TSUB21 (reference temperature) sensors are plugged in. It is controlled through a dedicated Python library.

A GoPro HERO4 (GoPro Inc., USA) is used for the animals' reaction tracking.

A Raspberry Pi 3B (Raspberry Pi Foundation, UK), is employed as the core of the acquisition module. All the data flow is controlled through it based on the *LIDO* architecture designed by the Laboratory of Applied Bioacoustics, UPC, Spain (André, et al., 2010; André, et al., 2011).

2.2.3. Control module

A UPC-owned facility is being adapted to accommodate the AquaVib setup in order to provide suitable conditions for water quality and temperature control where the animals are held. This facility includes two 2000-litre tanks, a sand and active carbon filter (Granada 500, Kripsol, Spain), associated temperature control systems (TK 5K, Teco s.r.l, Italy), and two inline water pumps, for both the filtration and the refrigeration circuits (see Figure 23 in section A.2. Outdoor facilities).

Automated remote control of the water flow from the large tanks to the AquaVib acoustic chamber is achieved through a set of three electro valves, and a control relay (Yocto-Latched Relay, Yoctopuce, Switzerland).

The controlled water flow required by the respirometry system (<500 ml/min), is provided by a small inline water pump (Syncra NANO, SICCE, Italy), and a fine-control stopcock to adjust the water flow delivered by the pump.

A dedicated web server is used for real-time monitoring of acquired signals, and to visualize essential test parameters (e.g. spectrograms, water temperature and dissolved oxygen levels, SPL and SVL in third-octave bands), using a 27-inch monitor.

³ Due to an unexpected malfunctioning of the flush-mounted hydrophones, the UPC researchers have temporally substituted them with a pair of UPC-owned HTI-99-HF hydrophones (High Tech, Inc., USA).

2.2.4. Support module

In order to minimise structural- and ground-borne vibrations of the water column, the shakers-tube module is held and supported by a steel frame structure (5 mm-square structural steel bar), Each shaker is set on top of a sliding platform, to enable adjustment of their positions relative to the mounted acoustic chamber.

The structure includes a water basin which ensures that the acoustic chamber can be filled and emptied without any air bubbles becoming entrapped in the water column.

A 400 kg-electric hoist is mounted at the top of the structure to assist the operational handling and accurate positioning of the heavy acoustic chambers relative to the shakers.

The whole AquaVib system is securely bolted down onto a 20 cm-thick concrete platform at the outdoor facilities of the LAB.

3. System characterization

Beforehand, it is essential to stress the fact that due to an unexpected malfunctioning of the flush-mounted hydrophones, the UPC researchers have temporarily substituted them with a pair of UPC-owned HTI-99-HF hydrophones (High Tech, Inc., USA). Unfortunately, they do not fit the design of the system, so they were temporarily adapted to the transparent chamber.

For this reason, the reported data in the following sections are based on measurements undertaken on the transparent chamber, which can be considered as the worst-case scenario in terms of comparison of the sound field components, i.e. it has the narrowest useable frequency band among the three acoustic chambers.

Characterization tests on both the large- and the short-steel chambers will be included in deliverable D.3.9

3.1. Preliminary results

From literature (Helmholtz, 1863; Kirchhoff, 1868; Kundt, 1868; Weston, 1953; Tjeldeman, 1975; Fuller & Fahy, 1982), it is clear that sound field characterization in tubes has been a subject of study for more than a century now, underlining its complexity in terms of all the factors at play. Considering, on top of this, a pair of interacting ED shakers as sound sources add even more complexity to the system characterization.

An extensive literature search did not reveal any publicly-available data on the characterization of a similar setup, i.e. a pair of opposite ED shakers enclosing at both ends and simultaneously exciting a water volume. Furthermore, none of the vibration-testing industry experts that were consulted could provide relevant information for this specific scenario. Consequently a large array of test investigations were required in order to gain familiarity with the underlying phenomena, and to fine-tune the setup. The following key factors were investigated: dimension and material of the acoustic chamber, the effect of shakers facing each other, mass payload, sensor locations, membrane materials, air-bubble presence in the water volume, limitations on the system response correction, structural- and ground-borne vibrations, reliable metabolic rate assessment in large water volumes.

The initial round of testing revealed that the response of each shaker is strongly affected by the presence of its opposite number (*facing* effect), with an incompressible volume of water in between. Furthermore, the characteristics of the acoustic chamber employed to hold the water, coupled with the mechanical matching impedance of the shaker pair creates a complex vibration field. In order to compensate for this whole system response, the stereo input signal would require conditioning with a correction routine.

3.2. System response

Figure 9 shows the estimated ratio of the sound particle velocity level (SVL) spectrum to the spectrum of the input signal (a band pass-filtered (10 Hz-1 kHz) white noise, in volts). The so-called Frequency Response Functions (FRF) for the shakers. Here, both shakers were uncoupled from the rest of the system, and no payload was applied to their moving elements.

To compute the FRF curves, the time-averaged mean-square sound particle acceleration level, re $1 \mu\text{m/s}^2$, independently measured at the moving elements of both shakers were transformed to SVL using equation (1) (see section 1.2). Normalization was applied by dividing the FRF curves by their peak values, to scale them for comparison with the oncoming ones.

Figure 9 – Scaled FRF spectrum in decidecades bands, in dB, (continuous and dashed blue lines), independently measured for both shakers uncoupled with no mass payload on top. Aside, the scaled background noise levels (continuous and dashed red lines) measured at two different days.

Both FRF curves (in continuous and dashed blue lines respectively) present a peak around the 100 and 125 Hz decidecades bands, resembling a mass-spring system. A secondary-sharp peak is present below the 25 Hz decidecade band, which is also shown by the two scaled background noise spectrums computed from recordings on two different days (in continuous and dashed red lines respectively). This low-frequency energy contribution is most probably derived from environmental noise sources caught by the accelerometers (e.g. road traffic, ground-borne vibrations from the nearby harbour, etc.).

Figure 10 and Figure 11 show the AquaVib scaled FRF curves in decidecades bands in both configurations, i.e. AP and PM, based on both the hydrophones and the accelerometer readings respectively. For the latter, equation (1) was again applied to compute the sound particle velocity response of the system. A band pass-filtered (10 Hz-1 kHz) white noise was used as the input signal for both shakers.

Please note that the scaling of the FRF curves was computed based on the highest magnitude relative to each pair of sensors, and for each configuration. Thus a relative correction is applied on each channel of the target signal (e.g. Container ship URN).

Figure 10 - Normalized FRF of the AquaVib with the transparent acoustic chamber in the two configurations (AP, PM), at the two hydrophone locations, i.e. End hyd.: 5 cm from the right shaker, and Centre hyd.: at the longitudinal middle point of the acoustic chamber, expressed in scaled Sound Pressure Level (SPL).

Figure 11 - Normalized FRF of the AquaVib with the transparent acoustic chamber in both configuration (AP, PM), at the two accelerometer locations, expressed in scaled Sound Particle Velocity Level (SVL).

A comparison between the independently measured shakers' FRF curves (Figure 9), and the estimated AquaVib's FRF curves (Figure 10 and Figure 11), reflects the significant spectral colouration caused by the presence of those observed phenomena described before in section 3.1.

To correct the input signal based on the system's FRF curves, an equalization routine is performed before every test session, allowing the animals to be exposed to an energy distribution that is as closely matched as possible the spectrum of the signal of interest.

The equalisation routine procedure is performed as follows: a uniform white noise, band-pass filtered around 10 Hz and 1kHz, is played simultaneously in both shakers at the same input level for sixty seconds. Both SPL and SVL are computed from the signals recorded with both pairs of hydrophones and accelerometers respectively, which represent the AquaVib FRF at a specific scenario (e.g. with a sample of twenty mussels in seawater at 17°C). These are computed for both AP and PM configurations, by either applying a phase shift in the input signal of one of the shakers by 0 or 180 degrees respectively, i.e. driving them in the same or opposite direction. These curves are in turn inversely applied on the input stereo signal (e.g. container ship URN) to compensate it for the current system setup. This approach allows us to expose the animals to a target sound field which retains strong fidelity with the characteristics (in terms of spectrum and magnitude) of one of the two sound components, i.e. the acoustic pressure or the particle velocity, while significantly modifying its rate to the other depending on the selected configuration, i.e. AP or PM. This is further illustrated in sections 3.3 and 3.5.

We note that that the sound pressure FRF for the left shaker is based on data from the centre hydrophone. Given the nature of uncontrolled shell-borne vibrations transmitted from the transparent acoustic chamber to the water column, a hydrophone location closer to the right shaker would have been preferred as this would improve the quality of the derived FRF curve.

3.3. Playback sound equalization: Ship URN

A harmonized set of standard representative test signals has been developed within SATURN WP2 (see section 4 of SATURN Subtask 2.1.2). This set of signals contains the most relevant features of ship sound, and is being used by the SATURN WP3 groups to provide a consistent basis for intercomparison of results across the various types of laboratory-based experiments.

Figure 12 shows a comparison between the original artificially-synthesized container ship broadband URN signal, and the ones corrected based on the current setup, i.e. with the transparent acoustic chamber mounted. Note the spectral differences of the corrected target signal depending on the configuration mode and the reference sensor over which the system's FRF was computed (see Figure 9 and Figure 10 in the previous section).

Figure 12 - Spectral comparison of the original signal (black), with the FRF-corrected spectrum of the input signal at both channels (right: continuous, left: dashed) in both configurations (AP: blue, PM: grey), based on the hydrophones pair (top graph), and the accelerometers pair (bottom graph) .

3.4. Linearity assessment of the system

The linearity relation between the two sound field components was assessed for both configurations, i.e. AP and PM. A band pass-filtered (10 Hz-1 kHz) container ship URN was used as the target signal for both shakers at different input levels. An FRF correction was previously applied to it according to each of the two configurations (see Figure 12).

Figure 13 - SPL (dB re. 1µPa²) measured at different input powers in both AP and PM configurations. The legend shows the broad band SPL computed for each exposure level, as the mean value between each pair of sensors.

Figure 14 - SVL (dB re. 1 nm/s) measured at different input powers in both AP and PM configurations. The legend shows the broad band SVL computed for each exposure level, as the mean value between each pair of sensors.

As illustrated by Figure 13 and Figure 14, the AquaVib shows a linear relationship between the sound pressure component and the particle velocity component in both configurations from the 31 Hz decade band. In other words, a certain dB de/increment in the SPL spectrum is also reflected in the SVL spectrum in the same order of magnitude, and vice versa.

To explicitly illustrate the linearity property of the system, Table 1 shows the relative difference of both the measured SPL and SVL computed between the five different input levels in both AP and PM configurations.

Table 1 – Computed broadband SPL and SVL measured at different input powers in both AP (left bluish columns) and PM (right orange columns) configurations, employing a band-pass filtered FRF-corrected container ship URN from 10 to 1 kHz as input signal for both shakers.

SPL	Rel. diff.	SVL	Rel. diff.	SPL	Rel. diff.	SVL	Rel. diff.
153,8	-	116,1	-	154,1	-	120,7	-
161,9	8,1	116,1	0,0	161,9	7,8	127,1	6,5
167,0	5,1	116,2	0,2	167,1	5,2	132,0	4,8
171,2	4,2	116,5	0,3	170,8	3,7	135,9	4,0
174,7	3,5	117,1	0,5	175,0	4,2	140,4	4,4

Although considered correct in the PM configuration, we note the lack of linearity between the two sound components in the AP configuration. As was previously highlighted in section 3.2, this likely attributable to the constant source of background noise that dominates the broadband SVL at the lower frequency range, i.e. below the 31 Hz decade band, the influence of which tails-off as the input kinetic energy rises.

In Table 2 the bands worst affected the presence of the low-frequency background noise (<31 Hz) have been omitted to improve the linearity assessment of the current setup of the AquaVib. This influence is expected to be less with either of the two steel acoustic chambers in place. Efforts are ongoing to reduce the ground-borne transmission by acoustically isolating the whole structure through the incorporation silent blocks at the anchor points into the concrete platform).

Table 2 – Computed SPL and SVL in the frequency range from 31Hz to 1kHz decade bands, measured at different input powers in both AP (left bluish columns) and PM (right orange columns) configurations, employing a band-pass filtered FRF-corrected container ship URN from 10 to 1 kHz as input signal for both shakers.

SPL	Rel. diff.	SVL	Rel. diff.	SPL	Rel. diff.	SVL	Rel. diff.
153,5	-	90,5	-	153,9	-	118,7	-
161,6	8,1	97,8	7,4	161,7	7,8	126,7	7,9
166,7	5,1	102,9	5,0	166,9	5,2	131,7	5,1
170,9	4,2	106,8	3,9	170,6	3,7	135,8	4,0
174,4	3,5	110,2	3,4	174,8	4,2	140,2	4,5

3.5. AP- and PM-dominated sound fields comparison

In the absence of a standardised methodology for establishing the relative dominance of the two sound field components, based on internal project consultation with TNO, the UPC team have adopted an approach which is based on evaluating the relationship between the sound field components in terms of energy. This approach supports the creation of a sound field within the water column where either one or both the potential and the kinetic acoustic energies significantly contribute to the sound field.

3.5.1. Equal SPL

As noted previously, over the past decade several studies have demonstrated a range of sound pressure-related effects in marine invertebrates (Wale, et al., 2013; McCauley, et al., 2017; Day, et al., 2019; Wale, et al., 2019; Vazzana, et al., 2020; Vazzana, et al., 2020; Solé, et al., 2021; Solé, et al., 2022). By contrast, research on sound particle motion-related effects is still at a very early stage of development. This was the determining factor which supported the adoption of the sound pressure component as the baseline metric for subsequent investigations wherein the animals will be exposed to a potential energy spectrum in the same order of magnitude in both PM and AP configurations.

For validation purposes, an artificially synthesized container ship broadband sound file (SATURN Subtask 2.1.2), was used to illustrate the capability of the AquaVib to generate a sound field with a significantly higher kinetic energy spectrum in the PM configuration relative to AP configuration. The input signal was band-pass-filtered between 10 to 1000 Hz. Results from preliminary testing revealed that the most effective correction for the input signal to the target spectral energy was obtained from the hydrophones-based system's FRF for the AP configuration, and from the accelerometer-based system's FRF for the PM configuration (see Figure 12).

Figure 15 presents the SPL, dB re. $1\mu\text{Pa}^2$, in decidecades obtained in both configurations. Note that the input power has been adjusted to generate the same total potential energy within the water column in both configurations. The original ship sound spectrum (black) is plotted for spectral comparison.

We note that the response of the setup is closely matched with the original signal spectrum when operating in AP configuration. However this becomes noisier in PM configuration, and a deviation is expressed between 100 to 160 Hz decidecade bands. We anticipate that this effect will be reduced for the other two steel acoustic chambers where the shell-borne vibrations should be minimized thanks to their mechanical properties with a consequent improvement in their response to the input signal correction.

Figure 15 - Sound pressure spectrum, dB re. 1 μPa^2 , in both configurations (AP: blue, PM: grey), measured at the end (continuous line), and the centre (dashed line), hydrophone locations using a system’s FRF-corrected Container Ship broadband sound file as input signal. The original (black) Container Ship broadband spectrum has been adjusted for comparison.

Figure 16 shows the estimated SVL, dB re. 1 nm/s, derived from the accelerometer readings at both configurations.

Figure 16 - Sound particle velocity spectrum (re. 1 nm/s) in both configurations (AP: blue, PM: grey), measured at the left (continuous line), and at the right (dashed line), shakers, using a system’s FRF-corrected Container Ship broadband sound file as input signal. at each sensor.

From equation (6), an energy-based comparison between the sound fields generated in the two configuration modes can be performed as follows:

Table 3 – Energy-based comparison between the sound fields generated in both configurations at equal SPL. The mean broadband levels at every pair of sensors are considered a representative estimate of the average sound energy in the entire water column.

	Average broadband SPL, in dB re. 1 μPa^2	Average broadband SVL, in dB re. 1 $(\text{nm/s})^2$	$L_{E_{pot}} - L_{E_{kin}}$, in dB
AP configuration	169.8	116.1 // 107.4*	-10.3 // -1.6*
PM configuration	169.6	135.6 // 135.5*	-30.0 // -30.1*

*. For illustration purposes, the 10Hz decade band was subtracted to omit the energy contribution of the background noise (see Figure 9).

As illustrated by Table 3, the AquaVib setup shows a large difference in the sound kinetic component presented in the water column between the PM configuration and the AP configuration. This is similar to the pattern expected to be found under e.g. near-field conditions or close to acoustic boundaries for PM configuration, and a far-field pattern for the AP configuration (Popper & Hawkins, 2018).

This approach demonstrates the capability of the AquaVib to generate an equal sound pressure spectrum in either configuration, while producing a significantly more powerful sound particle velocity spectrum (>10 dB) in the PM configuration compared to the AP configuration, below the 316 Hz decade band.

3.5.2. Equal SVL

Following the rationale used in the previous section, the discrimination capability of the AquaVib is shown at equal SVL for both configuration modes. In this case, the accelerometer-based system’s FRF correction was found to be the most effective for both AP and PM configurations.

Figure 17 - Sound particle velocity spectrum (re. 1 nm/s) in both configurations (AP: blue, PM: grey), measured at the left (continuous line), and at the right (dashed line) shakers, using a system’s FRF-corrected Container Ship broadband sound file as input signal.

Figure 18 - Sound pressure spectrum, dB re. 1 μPa^2 , in both configurations (AP: blue, PM: grey), measured at the end (continuous line), and the centre (dashed line) hydrophone locations, using a system’s FRF-corrected Container Ship broadband sound file as input signal.

Table 4 – Energy-based comparison between the sound fields generated in both configurations at equal SVL. The mean broadband levels at every pair of sensors are considered a representative estimate of the average sound energy in the entire water column.

	Average broadband SVL, in dB re. 1 (nm/s) ²	Average broadband SPL, in dB re. 1 μPa ²	$L_{E_{pot}} - L_{E_{kin}}$, in dB
AP configuration	129.1 // 128.9*	175.1	-18.0 // -17.8*
PM configuration	128.9 // 128.7*	162.7	-30.2 // -30.0*

*. For illustration purposes, the 10Hz decade band was subtracted to omit the energy contribution of the background noise (see Figure 9). As the SVL was set much higher, the background noise contribution was much lower.

Although not as large as that found at equal SPL, the current setup of the Aquavib system effectively provides for an energy-based effect comparison at equal SVL, where a broadband SPL increment of over 12 dB in AP to PM configurations was obtained, which in turn produced a minimum 5 dB increment in SPL at any decade band of interest.

These findings support the assertion that the current setup provides the capability to conduct realistic animal exposure experiments for each of the sound components, separately.

3.6. Behaviour and physiological assessment

As previously described, the use of a built-in respirometry module and transparent acoustic chamber enables both behavioural and physiological responses to be observed during exposure experiments.

Figure 19 shows both the dissolved oxygen (dark blue) and water temperature (red) levels in the water volume from a 20-min preliminary test carried out with a batch of 20 adult mussels on October 3rd 2022. No sound was played during this run.

Before running the respirometry module, the animals were allowed to acclimate for thirty minutes whilst being flushed with fully oxygenated water volume at a constant temperature supplied by the pumping system from the external tanks.

During the respirometry test, 10% of the initial dissolved oxygen was allowed to be depleted before the automated trigger of the flushing pumps, to avoid animal stress caused by low oxygen levels (Ruiz-Ruiz, et al., 2019).

Figure 19 - Dissolved oxygen (dark blue) and water temperature (red) measured during a 20-min silent test conducted with 20 mussels adults in the AquaVib. Squared in light blue, the flushing cycle period. In dashed yellow and pink lines, the associated animals' O₂ consumption rate and the 'transition' period respectively.

Close monitoring of the high accuracy respirometry module for both water temperature and dissolved oxygen ensured that the water temperature could be maintained within the ± 0.5 °C boundaries throughout the duration of the exposure.

Furthermore the water flushing-cycle routine permits several replicates of the dissolved O₂ depletion curves to be logged, provided the duration of the exposure and/or the animals' O₂ consumption rates are sufficiently long to fit more than one complete O₂ depletion curve in a single exposure. The duration of the flushing cycle has to be adjusted to the water volume held by the acoustic chamber (highlighted in light blue square in Figure 19), in order to ensure O₂ conditions at the beginning of each respiration cycle are kept equal.

A steeper O₂ depletion rate is noted for the initial stage of the second respiration cycle (pink continuous line), which returns to the consumption rate associated with the animals shown in the first respiration cycle (dashed yellow lines). This is attributed to the water volume within the acoustic chamber not having been fully refreshed. This 'transition' period should be avoided to ensure a fully refreshed water volume at the end of each flushing cycle.

Concluding remarks

This document has presented a full characterization and validation of the AquaVib system which illustrates how the apparatus can be applied to advance our experimental knowledge on the acute and cumulative effects of underwater noise on aquatic species (SATURN objective 2).

A comprehensive battery of performance testing has demonstrated that the AquaVib satisfactorily achieves the required standards to be able to fulfil the main goal of Task 3.1, i.e. to identify and quantify possible risks, and acute and long-term impacts on marine invertebrates directly linked to the exposure to anthropogenic URN sources, assessing acoustic pressure and particle motion effects separately.

Key design innovations including the sensor-based FRF correction of the input signal to fit the energy distribution of the target URN source, mean that the AquaVib provides the UPC research team with a multimodal capability. This will enable investigation of possible physiological, pathological, and ultrastructural effects on invertebrate species across all stages of maturity, that may be associated with either of the two sound components that comprise low-frequency target sound cues.

A follow-up study is planned in order to obtain a more detailed characterization of the AquaVib with each of the two steel acoustic chambers using a new set of hydrophones. The results will be included in deliverable D3.9.

Additional adjustment, refinement and fine-tuning is ongoing in order to optimise system performance, within which a key priority will be to fully isolate the AquaVib from all extraneous ground-borne energy sources.

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Annex A – Construction process

A ca. year and a half R&D process produces details that continuously emerge and evolve driven by thoughtful planning, plus many unexpected events. The following pictures aim to illustrate some of the milestones during this process.

A.1. Preliminary tests

Figure 20 - Top- Experiment setup (unmounted). Bottom- setup calibration at the measurement location (metal plate), with a reference accelerometer attached to the shaker moving element.

Figure 21 - Top- Experiment setup (mounted). Bottom- Acquisition chain setup.

A.2. Outdoor facilities

Figure 22 - Concrete foundation for the installation of the AquaVib system.

Figure 23 - Water cooling-filtering UPC-owned system used to recirculate clean, oxygenated sea water to the AquaVib system through the two pipes that go into the ground. The two big white units are the coolers, and behind them the two black containers are filled with filtered-temperature controlled water up to 4000 L.

A.3. System construction

Figure 24 - Top- Metal bars preparation. Bottom- First welding points of the structure

Figure 25 - Top- Sliding bars installation. They allow the adjustment of the shakers location in the horizontal plane. Bottom- Shakers' support frame installed on a pair of sliding metal bars.

Figure 26 - Top- Metal plates polishing and epoxy primer application. Bottom- Grating to hold the water vessel used to fill the acoustic chambers (left), and epoxy primer application on the whole support structure (right).

Figure 27 - Painting process

Figure 28 - Flush hydrophone installation.